

Preparation of Lithium(triphenylsilyl)organocopper and Lithium(triphenylstannyl)phenylcopper and some Reactions of Lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper

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The preparation of lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper, its stannyl analogue and lithium(triphenylsilyl)methylcopper is reported. These reagents do not give a positive response to the Gilman colour test-1. The reaction of lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper with methyl iodide gives toluene (33%) and triphenylmethylsilane (32%), with benzyl chloride the same reagent gives diphenylmethane (100%), and with benzoyl chloride, it gives triphenylsilyl phenyl ketone (25%) and benzophenone (19%).

DUFFAUT and co-workers reported in 1978 the first successful preparation of lithiumbis(triorganosilyl)copper and its stannyl analogues and their successful application in the synthesis of silyl or stannyl ketones¹. Since then several reports have appeared; these described the preparation of many lithiumbis(triorganostannyl)coppers, the corresponding simple polymeric copper(I) reagents of the type R_3SnCu , and mixed cuprate reagents of general formula, $Li(R_3Sn)(PhS)Cu^{2-6}$. Also described recently are some organosilylcopper reagents^{7,8}. These reagents were employed successfully in the synthesis of many compounds in which the triorganotin or triorganosilyl moieties were transferred. We have been interested in studying the reactivity of mixed diorganohomocuprate reagents as potential agents for the transfer of one organic group in preference to the other, to various substrates^{9,10}. In this communication we would like to report the preparation of such mixed cuprate reagents as lithium(triphenylstannyl)phenylcopper, lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper and lithium(triphenylsilyl)methylcopper reagents, and describe some reactions of lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper.

Experimental

All reactions were carried out under a positive pressure of dry oxygen-free nitrogen atmosphere. The ethereal solvents were dried over sodium wire and distilled prior to use. Triphenylbromostannane and triphenylbromosilane were obtained commercially.

Lithium(triphenylstannyl)phenylcopper: Dark olive brown solution of triphenylstannyl lithium (prepared¹¹ from 0.01 mol triphenylbromostannane and 0.02 g-atom lithium in 100 ml THF at room temperature) was added to phenylcopper¹² (prepared from 0.01 mol phenylmagnesium bromide and 0.01

mol copper(I) iodide in 100 ml THF at -10° ¹³, previously cooled to -10° . The mixture was stirred for 0.5 h, during which period Gilman test-I¹⁴ was negative and a dark maroon coloured viscous solution was obtained. Oxygen was passed through the reagent thus prepared for 30 min at -10° , hydrolysed and worked up in the conventional way to give tetraphenyltin, m.p. 226° (lit.¹⁵ 226°).

Lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper: An olive-brown solution of triphenylsilyllithium¹¹ (prepared from 0.01 mol triphenylbromosilane and 0.02 g-atom lithium in 100 ml THF at room temperature for 4.5 h) in THF was added to a cooled (-15°) suspension of phenylcopper^{12,13} (prepared from 0.01 mol phenylmagnesium bromide and 0.01 mol copper(I) iodide at -10° in 100 ml THF). The mixture was stirred for 1 h at -15° . The dark homogeneous maroon coloured lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper gave a negative response to Gilman test-I¹⁴.

Lithium(triphenylsilyl)methylcopper: It was prepared in the same way as lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper except that methylcopper^{12,13} was used in place of phenylcopper. Methylcopper^{12,13} was prepared by reacting methylmagnesium iodide (0.01 mol) in ether (100 ml) with copper(I) iodide (0.01 mol) at -10° until Gilman test-I was negative. The dark viscous solution of lithium(triphenylsilyl)methylcopper did not give a positive response to Gilman test-I¹⁴ though triphenylsilyllithium did.

Reaction of lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper with methyl iodide: To lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper (prepared from 0.01 mol phenylcopper and 0.01 mol triphenylsilyllithium) in THF at -15° was added methyl iodide (0.03 mol) all at a time and the mixture stirred for 1 h at -15° , then at 0° for 0.5 h and finally at room temperature for 0.5 h.

The reaction mixture was hydrolysed with a saturated solution of ammonium chloride in aqueous ammonia, the organic material extracted in diethyl ether (3×30 ml) and the combined ether extract was washed several times with a saturated $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}-\text{NH}_3$ solution until the blue colour of the copper complex disappeared. The ether layer was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the solvent removed from the filtrate to give a brown liquid. Fractional distillation and column chromatography gave (i) toluene (33%) (identified by b.p., ir, glc) and (ii) triphenylmethylsilane, (32%), m.p., $65-6^\circ$ (lit.¹⁶ 67°); ν_{max} as expected; δ 7.6–7.3 (15H, m), 0.83 (3H, s). Some gummy mass was also obtained, but it could not be identified.

When the above reaction was carried out with 0.01 mol of methyl iodide instead of 0.03 mol under similar conditions the yields of the various products obtained, subsequent to usual aqueous work-up, are as follows: (i) toluene (a trace), and (ii) triphenylmethylsilane (40%) and an intractable gummy mass (0.89 g).

Reaction of lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper with benzyl chloride: To lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper (0.01 mol) kept at -15° was added benzyl chloride (0.01 mol) all at a time and the mixture was stirred at -15° for 1 h at 0° for 0.5 h and finally at room temperature for 0.5 h. The hydrolytic work-up as described above followed by separation of products by column chromatography and purification by distillation gave diphenylmethane in quantitative yield (purity 99.5% by glc), b.p., $259-60^\circ$ (lit.¹⁷ $261-62^\circ$); ν_{max} as expected; δ 7.22 (10H, s) and 4.30 (2H, s).

Reaction of lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper with benzoyl chloride: To lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper (0.01 mol) kept at -15° was added benzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) all at a time. The mixture was stirred at -15° for 1 h and at 0° for 0.5 h. After the usual work-up as described above and purification of the products by recrystallisation, the following compounds were obtained, (i) triphenylsilyl phenyl ketone (25%), m.p., $107-08^\circ$ (lit.¹⁸ $107-09^\circ$); ν_{max} 1665 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 7.9–7.3 (m); and (ii) benzophenone (19%) (identified by ir, nmr and glc). Some gummy mass was also present.

Results and Discussion

Lithium(triphenylsilyl)organocopper and lithium-(triphenylstannyl)phenylcopper reagents were prepared by the following reaction,

where, M=Si, R=Me or Ph; and M=Sn, R=Ph.

The formation of these reagents in solution was indicated by their colour change from the olive-green colour of the silyllithium or stannylithium reagents to a maroon colour. Furthermore, these reagents gave negative responses to Gilman test-I¹⁴.

It may be mentioned that usually all reactive organometallic reagents, e.g. the Grignard reagents and lithium reagents, including silyllithium and stannylithium reagents, give a positive response to the test¹⁹, but organocopper reagents do not being less reactive²⁰ than the corresponding magnesium or lithium reagents^{2,21}. These mixed lithium silyl- or stannyl-copper reagents react vigorously with oxygen and moisture in the air. Thus they were prepared in a dry oxygen-free nitrogen-atmosphere.

The reaction of lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper with methyl iodide (in 1:3 molar ratio) gave, subsequent to hydrolytic work-up, toluene (33%), and triphenylmethylsilane (32%). These two compounds were probably formed by the Corey—Posner type of coupling reaction²²,

Thus, the cuprate reagent was unable to transfer either one or the other of the two organic groups to the methyl iodide substrate when the latter was used in large excess. However, when the same reaction was carried out with one-equivalent of methyl iodide, rather than three-equivalents, the yield of triphenylmethylsilane was 40% and that of toluene diminished to a trace. This may be explained if one assumes that the triphenylsilyl group of the above cuprate reagent is more reactive than the phenyl group. Thus in the presence of an insufficient amount of methyl iodide only the triphenylsilyl group was preferentially transferred to the substrate. This selectivity seemed to be destroyed when there were too many molecules to react with. However, opposite selectivity was observed when the substrate was changed from methyl iodide to benzyl chloride. Diphenylmethane was obtained quantitatively. The steric factor may be responsible for this unusual changeover in chemoselectivity.

The reaction of lithium(triphenylsilyl)phenylcopper with a different type of halide, benzoyl chloride, on the other hand, gave products which seemed to originate from indiscriminate transfer of the organic groups to the substrate,

A possible explanation for this poor selectivity is probably the high reactivity of the substrate towards the cuprate reagent.

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